

iPhone SE Setup

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Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

No changes first screen

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

Create password 1234

I choose to transfer from Android.

Transfer Account

From Google Pixel 3 to Samsung A03 Core

NO SIM

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

It is necessary to download Move to iPhone in Android phone..

In the terms and conditions can be read that the data that would be migrated for the Android device are Media files (Photos, videos, Movies, Books), Application data, Metadata to identify applications, movies and books and Google and Gmail usernames

Images from Samsung A3 Core

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

There are two ways to transfer the data. By cable (not included) and by WiFi.

We choose the option to connect via Wifi using a code. Transfer failed because Samsung A03Core could not find the iPhone.

New Account Setup

NO SIM

Factory Reset – New Account Set Up

After the transfer account failed. We choose the option to “Don’t transfer anything”

We choose to create an Apple ID to download apps later.

Factory Reset – New Account Set Up

We use a Google account.

It is necessary to enter a phone to verify the identity. I am using my personal phone for this step

Factory Reset – New Account set up.

Terms and conditions, update phone screen, location services and Set Up mobile service are the same as in previous updates.

Factory Reset – New Account set up.

Screen time, and analytics screen no different from previous setup.

Factory Reset – New Account set up.

The first screen shows the Safari, Apple TV, Maps, Health, etc. widgets.

The first time we go to safari, we see the “About Your Default Browser” screen. We observe the same browsers as in the previous setup (+ Web@Work), but in a random order.

Factory Reset – New Account set up.

After selecting a browser, a new screen will welcome you to the App Store to download the selected browser.

If we select another browser instead of Safari, we will redirect to the App store to download the selected browser. After initiating the download, the screen will disappear leaving us in the main Safari screen. Once the download is complete, we receive a notification that the browser is the default.

It is not possible to choose more than one browser in the “Choose Your Default Browser”

Factory Reset – New Account set up.

The initial search is not different from previous set ups.

When you press “Send”, a screen will appear with different options, including “Open in Chrome”.

The default search engine in Safari is Google. To change this is necessary to change it in phone Settings > Safari App > Search Engine. The available options are Google (Default), Yahoo, Bing, DuckDuckGo, Ecosia.

Factory Reset – New Account set up.

The first time you open Google Chrome, you will be asked which search engine you want to use by default. With the message "These are shown in random order. You can change your default at any time".

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

Go to Settings > Default Browser Application. The two available options are shown (Safari, Chrome)

Searching for browsers in the App Store, we see Firefox in the first place as sponsored browser.

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

We go into our Apple ID. We see that it is linked to a Gmail account,

Apps that store information using iCloud. We see Safari, but no Google Chrome.

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

The first time we open Mail, we can now choose a different provider account. I choose Google, after entering my credentials, the "Sign in to iOS asked for permission to share data" screen appears. There is no option to avoid this and link Mail.

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

Still unable to download an app from the Apple Store.

Factory Reset – Transfer Account

No SIM.

Download the Google apps; Drive, Maps, Google.

Opening Google Maps for the first time is necessary to give permission to determine the location. Ask Google App for real-time updates.

Principals' findings. iPhone SE Setup.

Transferring Account from Samsung A03 Core to iPhone - In the terms and conditions can be read that the data that would be migrated for the Android device are Media files (Photos, videos, Movies, Books), Application data, Metadata to identify applications, movies and books and Google and Gmail usernames.

There are two ways to transfer the data from other phones. By cable (not included) and by Wi-Fi.
Transfer failed by Wi-Fi because Samsung A03Core could not find the iPhone

The first time we go to safari, we see the “About Your Default Browser” screen. We observe the same browsers as in the previous setup (+ Web@Work), but in a random order.

It is not possible to choose more than one browser in the “Choose Your Default Browser” Screen

The default search engine in Safari is Google. To change this is necessary to change it in phone Settings > Safari App > Search Engine. The available options are Google (Default), Yahoo, Bing, DuckDuckGo, Ecosia.

The first time Google Chrome is open, you will be asked which search engine you want to use by default. With the message "These are shown in random order. You can change your default at any time".

The first time we open Mail, we can now choose a different provider account, I choose Google. After entering my credentials, the "Sign in to iOS asked for permission to share data" screen appears. There is no option to avoid this and link Mail.